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Reconstructing Educational Research in Tertiary Institutions: Strategy for Sustainable Development in the Third World

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Abstract

In common parlance, research is simply the process of finding out details about things, events, issues and situations for the purpose of understanding and utilization of specific context. It is a conscious effort to provide more knowledge about that which is already known. Research attempts to take the world one step further in its attempt to grapple with and secure the best from any situation. This paper attempts a reconstruction of the conduct and utilization of research tools by our intellectuals in Nigeria to achieve the desired development. In attempting to refocus education in Nigeria, there is need to explore how we have failed to utilize the tools of research for advancement in our educational endeavor. What impact, if any has the research conducted in Nigeria had on the society? In what ways can our educational institutions be made more research oriented? To what areas do we need to direct research and what are the possible outcomes? Research at other levels of education is of no less important to society as research in tertiary institutions. How can research scholars then adequately utilize the tools of research to bring about the desired development in our educational system and the 3rd world as a whole?

Introduction

Research is basically an intellectual activity which is carried out to find a solution to identified problems. As the main source of skilled manpower, research and ideas, intellectuals of universities the world over, bear the principal responsibility for building and steering the economy in the direction of sustainable change and development. Their role in academics and research provides support for the innovation and reinnovation system of any economy,

third world or advanced. Their primary role of teaching assists the improvement of institutional regime through the training of competent professionals needed for adaptable labor force for sound developments. For instance, in Nigeria, a lot has gone into teacher preparation recently at higher level, in terms of high quality course content, time tested and proven methodology, practical teaching skills, sociological and psychological foundation, professionalism and sound research orientation apart from the huge capital investment in human and material resources (Isyaku, 2005).

To successfully fulfill the educational research and informational functions in this 21st century, tertiary educational institution needs to be able to respond effectively to changing education and teaching needs, adapt to a rapidly shifting tertiary education landscape and adopt flexible modes of organization and operation.

It is important to note that advanced training and research programmes are being maintained at the post graduate level for the main reason of growth and development. According to recent studies on the determinant of national innovative capacity, these countries mostly the advanced, that have located a higher share of their research and development activity in their educational sector have been able to achieve high patenting productivity (UNESCO, 2003). The rapid transformation of the "Asian Tigers" that is, South Korea, Taiwan, Singapore, Japan etc. is the outcome of the right application of research techniques (Asim, Kalu & Ekwueme, 2007).

The research industry occupies a very prominent position in the Nigerian economy as in other 3rd world countries. In recognition of its role, government established the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), which has in the last few years tried to bring to the front burner the course of research and development in education through her statutory responsibilities prominent among which is focusing research in education that will drive public policy in

the sector. The world has always progressed on the basis of sound research conduct and utilization. Educational research in particular, if properly utilized will ensure better planned and executed educational policies and programmes and better management of educational system with the attendant impact on National development.

In the 3rd world countries, not much has been accomplished through research. So much blame has been placed on the various agents of education. Our intellectuals are not left out of this. Durosaro (2010) has observed a great deal of disenchantment on the part of the teachers, leading to ineffectiveness and inefficiency of the system. Of course, no educational system can be better than those who operate it, that is, the teachers who constitute the intellectual resource pool which ensures that present and future human and social capacity can be developed, managed and sustained. This is what makes research in the hands of intellectuals, a key in the development process of the advance countries of USA, United Kingdom, West Germany and Japan among others. The question now is how much of the benefits of research in education are being utilized for development of the 3rd world countries? This is what this paper is out to address.

It is believed that a number of factors has been assumed to limit university research in Nigeria. They authors have examined this limitation from the point of view of the following:

- * Poor conduct and limited focus of education research
- * Lack of motivation arising from poor appraisal of research intellectuals.
- * Inadequate funding and utilization of research by our educational system.

It is on the basis of these problems limiting research in education, and thus growth and development in Nigeria, that the authors elected to dwell on the issue, "Reconstructing educational research in tertiary institutions: strategy for the sustainable development in the 3rd world". Thus research having been identified as engine of growth and development in advance countries and researchers playing a fundamental role in the delivery process, intellectuals must seek strategies to reconstruct the paradigm in educational research and developments. **State of Educational Research in Nigeria**

Research and development are in fact necessary for survival. It creates innovation in all human endeavors. It makes it possible for new products,

processes and services to be developed. It is central to the success of a knowledge-driven economy and in creating wealth and employment. For the academia, its use is found in staff motivation among other things. But in Nigeria and other underdeveloped nations, there is no doubt today that research endeavors have reached a very low level, in Nigerian tertiary institutions. For instance, in an article, Okebukola (2000) painted a picture of the state of research in tertiary institutions in Nigeria and came to the conclusion that the quality and quantity of research had reached an all-time "low". It is revealed that over time, the number of quality articles published by intellectuals in international journals would have decreased steadily.

In another article, he noted that there are presently few active journals in the country and that many reputable journals of old are dead. Similarly, there are several new ones which did not go beyond maiden editions and in the word of the author, "they had vol. 1: no.1 and no. 2 or Vol. II thereafter". With this situation, it becomes difficult to assess the direction of research in the country. The present publish or perish syndrome in our tertiary institutions has not helped matters either. In order to publish and not perish, intellectuals engage in a lot of fraudulent practices such as:

- * issuance of acceptance letters without articles
- * papers published without assessment
- * contracting of lecturers to write articles
- * Submission of five or more acceptance letters for promotion.
- * Plagiarism
- * patronizing journals published outside the academic circle
- * floating of unrecognized journals by academic association for money making
- * embarking on researches that do not contribute to national development
- * patronizing quack and roadside publishing houses

From the foregoing discussions, intellectuals and policy makers should focus on strategies that will redirect and redefine the objectives of research from mere production of papers towards the enhancement of educational practice. The time has come when the idea of publish or perish must be jettisoned. A reconstructive process that should place teaching as a number one priority of all universities and research as number two should be immediately sought after as this has become the trend in the world today (Sofoluwe, 2002), and all university

lecturers must acquire effective methods of teaching through organized courses and seminars sponsored by their respective institutions. It is important to emphasize that our students and the entire system of education need good and effective research scholars who can first and foremost teach the skills required to carry out good research.

Conduct and Focus of Research in Nigeria

Intellectuals in Nigeria embarking on university research do so for academic progression, and among students, it is done for the purpose of graduation. This is a very limited focus of research and development in the country. Since research outputs are not needed beyond the immediate use for the promotion and graduation, they are carried out with less empirical proof of applicability.

The sub-Saharan Africa and other under-developed nations have been slow in their process of development and in their integration into the global economy as a result of the limited focus in research endeavours. When compared with the fast developing Asian Countries and other developed countries of USA, UK, Germany, Japan etc, they are being left behind. On the average, the economies of nations in the sub-region have contracted with unemployment, poverty, diseases and crime rate increasing, and education levels rising less rapidly than in the more globalized countries (Obioma, 2010). He noted that a recent World Bank report indicates that poverty has in fact doubled in Nigeria in the last 20 years.

According to the Longe commission of 1992 on the review of higher education in Nigeria, research should be both of a basic nature and of problem solving value and geared towards seeking solution to national and local developmental problems. The universities should publicize research activities and research results and make more serious effort to seek involvement of the private sectors to commercialize the inventions and discoveries.

Strategy that will foster strategic planning approach to research projects, that has direct relevance to educational practice should be adhered to. The planning and execution should be in collaboration with the likely end users of the research findings. The invaluable impact of this strategy, that is, collaborative research has placed Japan as the foremost in development in the world today (Okonjo, 2008).

With regard to research collaboration, the Federal Government of Nigeria provided one such research facilitating system by way of Microsatellite Low Earth Orbit (LEO), launched in September, 2003, by National Space Research

and Development Agency (NASRDA) in collaboration with the Surrey Satellite Corporation of the UK (Ubong & Oguzor, 2003). The slow pace of development in the country does not, however, show any private enterprises have joint research programmes with local universities. For instance, in Japan, the Semi Conductors Technology Academic Research Centre, a private enterprise, works with universities on semi conductor research. ([http:// www.starc.or.jp](http://www.starc.or.jp).2006). Proof of accessibility of such facilities to research practitioners in the 3rd world who must make use of very important information and data collectable from such sources for theoretical and applied researches is yet to be established.

Appraisal System of Research Intellectuals in Nigeria

Appraisal practice of intellectuals in the universities is a tool of evaluation which is concerned with looking at how they put their ideas into practice in education and consequently make them effective. It is geared towards assessing accountability or course effectiveness or attainment marched to normative goals. Like any other form of evaluation tool, the system of appraisal in our universities is often perceived as inquisitional and threatening with the result that the changes that are associated with the appraisal may remain unrealizable.

In all Nigerian universities, appraisal has concentrated on recognized publications, such as: textbook published from research work, tertiary textbook in relevant disciplines, editorship of book, an article in learned journal, a chapter in referred book, referred conference/seminar paper, distant public lectures, research/technical report, monographs, contributions to universities/country, academic recognition/distinction; but referred conference paper in proceedings according to Mordi (2002), is not usually accepted in most first generation universities.

Other appraisal criteria adopted by most universities are academic qualification/professional, teaching and current research. However, the weighting of these items varies from one university to another but the emphasis has remained on publication. This has been seen as a diversion from the research excellence expected from our universities; the obvious emphasis now being on research output which has only encouraged rise of mediocrity (Mordi, 2002). The author is of the opinion that the form of research existence that will emanate from proper appraisal should demand that the Universities should source for funds and commission studies, hold seminars/workshops aimed at explaining the complexities at hand by bringing universities together in collaborative efforts, pooling of resources especially of expertise, etc.

In the meanwhile, universities can take the following steps to reduce the inquisitorial and threatening nature of appraisal practices:

- * Re-examine the appraisal criteria to make them more realistic
- * A lessening of appraisal focus on publication; a review of the criteria for weighting same.
- * Adequate weighing of teaching in the appraisal criteria
- * Rating of academic staff on all the three levels of their function in the university teaching, research and community service.
- * A review of the recruitment practice. All staff vacancies should be advertised to enable universities draw from a large pool as this would help to eliminate academic staff who would be unable to cope from the start. When all these are done, appraisal in our universities will fulfill the role of fostering confidence and enhancing the performance of intellectuals in their daily assignments.

Utilization of Research in Educational Institutions

Research involves seeking knowledge both for itself and for practical use. Its results in tertiary institutions should either deepen people's understanding of a phenomenon or enhance its utility in specific contexts.

In order to adequately utilize the results of educational research, the process and product of research should be published, thereby advancing the knowledge about the object of research among both the researchers and users of the research endeavours, as this will help us to foster the realization of the first purpose of advancing knowledge.

Utilization of research finding in the 3rd world countries, particularly in Nigeria where the backwardness has been attributed to the inadequate utilization of findings and results of research, needs urgent attention if sustainable development must be ushered in, in this 21st century.

In fact, Ubong & Oguzor (2003) noted that the development part of research involving the use of the results of research for practical ends is obviously lacking in Nigeria. This is why such practical outcomes in form of development of new product or improvement of an existing one have not reached the level of the developed countries. An example is the research into the use of solar energy to power cars.

Funding of Research in Tertiary Institutions

The rationale for research lies in the need to comprehend deeply the world around us and possibly use such enhanced understanding to make the world a better place for man. However, the activity of research is not only usually time consuming but also expensive. The modern industrialized countries recognize the fact that research requires the talent, skills and expenditure of vast sum of money and so earmark substantial portion of their budget for it. Infact, the requirement of vast sums of money is indeed the crux of the issue of research.

Ubong and Oguzor (2003) assert that the world over , funds for research come primarily from government and business firms. Others include foundations and professional societies. In a number of countries, funding of research is a collaborative effort with government, bilateral and multilateral agencies, foundations, businesses and tertiary educational institutions working in projects of interest. Collaborating between tertiary educational institutions, research centres and the government in funding of research and this is a multi-billion dollar or pound engagement in the United States of America and the United Kingdom (UK) respectively. Hero (2003) Website indicates that over 14 billion pounds is spent each year by a combination of public bodies, private enterprises and international organizations for research funding in the U.K. It is noted that U.S and other advanced countries spend huge sums on research and development. This is not the situation in 3rd world countries.

Okonjo (2008) noted that in Nigeria, the situation is such that the government spends only 0.1 percent of her gross domestic product on research and development while Japan, the foremost country in the world in this sphere of development spends 2.8 percent out of a much larger gross domestic product than Nigeria on research and development.

Iyela (2002) while examining the small budgetary allocation to research in Nigerian educational institutions, it was noted that in a period of economic distress, other items of expenditure capital project, salaries and allowances which always receive substantial share of the budget, have to be secondary to the prime objectives of teaching, learning and research, research being the activity which guarantees that what is taught and how it is taught is being undertaken. Closely related to the problem of lack of funds are inadequate research grants to researchers. Only few intellectuals have access to research grants in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. Another problem arises from the fact that the few who have been fortunate to receive, do not give proper account for such grants to enable them qualify for another one. Many researchers have been known to divert a substantial part of research grants to other uses, thereby abandoning the research.

The various intellectuals and government have tended to pay less interest in research activity irrespective of the priority which the National Policy on Education pays to it. The NPE (FRN, 1998) has research and development as one of the ways of achieving the goals of educational services in section 9. Section 8 (c) states, "Federal and state governments shall set aside a pre-determined percentage of their educational funds to support educational research, development and innovations" (p. 40).

The orientation of government towards research in practice as against the theoretical emphasis, as gleaned from the poor budget allocations to tertiary institutions has been known to affect the motivation of many intellectuals in our institutions. The use of research for the academia, according to Cogburn (2003) is found in staff motivation among other things. He noted that a strong research base is essential to attracting and retaining the best quality staff and students, and providing a firm foundation for a modern knowledge - led economy.

It is important to emphasize that for quality education with research as one avenue to its reality, more funds and grants should be allocated for research by state and federal governments as well as by industries the way it is being done in developed countries.

Towards Optimizing Research Effort / output for meaningful and Sustainable Development in the 3rd World.

So far, effort has been made to address a number of research- related factors that have kept the economies of the 3rd world countries low. At the same time, a number of strategies have been highlighted in the paper which are available tools in the hands of our intellectuals to transform the nations. Such new strategies are the main mechanism through which the results of research are infused into the educational system, transforming the technical and other bases of development in the 3rd world. Strategies highlighted by the study for sustainable development of the 3rd world are summarized as follow:

- * Attitude of government to research must change. The government should recognize the critical role the intellectuals play in research with respect to overall development by giving them all the necessary supports.
- * Intellectuals in the 3rd world countries if financially empowered and granted adequate accessibility to funds could achieve as much as researchers in developed countries.

- * Within institutions should exist research monitoring teams to ensure non diversion of research grants.
 - * Companies' sponsorship of academicians in research should be encouraged.
 - * Collaborative research with the private sector is a powerful strategy to adopt as this will generate new products, services and technology for the overall development of the nations of the 3rd world.
 - * Appraisal criteria that will motivate and encourage rather than threaten research practitioners should be adopted.
 - * The issue of conduct, focus and utilization of research can be addressed by redefining research objectives from mere paper production towards the improvement of educational practice.
 - * Re- planning and execution should be an integrated approach, an approach that will have direct relevance to educational practice. Planning and execution should be in collaboration with the likely end users of the research findings.
 - * There should be coordinating centers for channeling research findings to relevant end users by way of publication and monitoring plans for application of findings.
- (10) Themes for coordinated research geared towards solving specific educational problems, should be adopted by departments and faculties.
- (11) Intellectuals and other research practitioners should always keep the real motive for education research in sharp focus. And this is to use research as a means of reconstructing and revamping the education industry especially of the 3rd world and thereby usher them into a fit state of competitiveness in the global market.

Conclusion

This paper attempts to examine the strategies to be employed by intellectuals to reconstruct university research in the third world in order to transform these nations from economically dependent to developed countries. To this end, the recommendations made and based on sound research conduct and utilization, can move the nations of these countries to the desired level of development. And realizing that this vehicle of development led reconstruction has to be driven by them, intellectuals must arise to their basic responsibility as no nation can rise above standards set by its intellectuals.

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